

Effects of WABE 300 EC Fungicide against Stem rust (*Puccinia graminis f.sp.tritici*) and Yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis f.sp.tritici*) of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*)

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Abstract

Ethiopia is the largest producer of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in the sub-Saharan Africa. Despite its importance as food and industrial crop, wheat production and productivity around the globe is hampered by a number of factors including biotic and abiotic stresses as well as low adoption of new agricultural technologies. Of the biotic stresses, diseases caused by fungi are the most important factors constraining wheat production. Among the diseases stem rust and yellow rust, are highly destructive diseases of wheat worldwide. The recurrent occurrence of yellow rust and stem rust, diseases in the study area causes considerable yield losses. To prevent the yield loss due to these diseases, farmers used different fungicides released for either wheat diseases or other crop diseases alone or in a combination of fungicides with each other due to the disease's aggressiveness under field conditions. Field experiment was conducted to verify the effectiveness of the Wabe300 EC fungicide (Tebuconazole 225g/L + Triadimenol 75g/L) relative to another promising standard fungicide, Royal 750 WDG, for the management of stem rust and yellow rust of wheat. The experiment was conducted at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha, on farmers' field in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five replications during 2023 cropping season. The experiment result confirmed that, fungicide treated plots were showed significant difference compared to the control treatments in all variables. Wabe 300 EC foliar application at the rate of 0.5 L/ha with 200 liter water per hectare was highly effective in controlling yellow and stem rust of wheat and increased grain yield of wheat. Hence, it is recommended for registration for the management of stem and yellow rust in wheat production. During the growing periods, no foliar toxic effect was observed from the effect of any tested fungicides.

Keywords: *Wheat, Yellow Rust, Stem Rust, Verification, Fungicide.*

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Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum spp.*) is one of the foremost cereal crops produced worldwide (FAOSTAT, 2021; USDA, 2022). Ethiopia is the largest producer of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in the sub-Saharan

Africa. Wheat in Ethiopia ranked 2nd cereal crop grown next to Tef, and it covers 1,897,405.05 hectares on which more than 5.78 million tons of grains were produced in the country (CSA, 2021). Durum and bread are the two major wheat types produced in the country whose proportion in 1991 was about 60 and 40%, respectively (Eshetu and Zerihun, 2003). Durum and bread wheat are indigenous to Ethiopia and have been cultivated since prehistoric period in the highlands. The crop is a key staple food crop for most food insecure people where the areas are characterized by shortages of food and animal feeds (USDA, 2022; Anteneh and Asrat, 2020; FAOSTAT, 2021). Despite its importance as food and industrial crop, wheat production and productivity around the globe is hampered by a number of factors including biotic and abiotic stresses as well as low adoption of new agricultural technologies (Zegaye T *et al.*, 2001). Of the biotic stresses, diseases caused by fungi are the most important factors constraining wheat production. Yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*), stem rust (*P. graminis* f.sp. *tritici*), leaf rust (*P. triticina*) and Septoria diseases especially *Septoria tritici* blotch (STB) are prevalent throughout the country and major disease of wheat in all wheat growing areas of the country causing serious economic losses (Hailu E and Woldeab G. 2015),(Eyal Z. 1999) and Ghaffary *et al.*, 2012). In another study wheat rusts; stem rust (*Puccinia graminis* f sp. *tritici*), leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina*) and yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*) were reported as the major biotic wheat production constraints (Hei *et al.*, 2018). Among the diseases stem rust and yellow rust, are highly destructive diseases of wheat worldwide. Under field conditions, sometimes several diseases come simultaneously at the same time if there are a favorable environment, susceptible host, and virulent pathogens (Agrios, 2005). In the study areas, there is high yield losses were recorded due to stem and yellow rust diseases of wheat. Early literature reported that under favorable conditions these diseases could destroy the entire wheat crop (Roelfs *et al.*, 1985; Marja *et al.*, 2020). The recurrent occurrence of yellow rust and stem rust, diseases in the study area causes considerable yield losses. To prevent the yield loss due to these diseases, farmers used different fungicides released for either wheat diseases or other crop diseases alone or in a combination of fungicides with each other due to the disease's aggressiveness under field conditions. On the other hand unwise use of fungicides might favor the development of resistance by pathogens. Research reports support the fact that unwise use of fungicides has led to the development of resistance to the pathogen (Roelfs *et al.* 1985; Green *et al.* 1990). Measures using appropriate management options, like proper fungicides, to reduce sources of infection and prevent the spread of disease are of great importance in controlling wheat diseases during the growing periods. Thus, there is a need for alternative and effective fungicides through the introduction of a new fungicide or different formulations of the existing fungicides with the same active ingredient that may continue to be introduced by the pesticide companies.

Therefore, the efficacy of the newly introduced fungicides on stem and yellow rust of wheat should be regularly tested and verified before introducing them to the production systems. Based on the above background, Areka Agricultural Research Center has been designated by the Ministry of Agriculture through the Southern Agricultural Research Institute to test the efficacy of the new fungicide, Wabe 300 EC against stem rust and yellow rust of wheat during the 2023 cropping season. Therefore, the objective of the study was to evaluate the efficacy of the fungicide Wabe 300 EC (Tebuconazole 225g/L + Triadimenol 75g/L) relative to another promising standard fungicide, Royal 750 WDG, for the management of stem rust and yellow rust of wheat for registration purpose.

Material and Methods

Descriptions of the Study Areas

The study was carried out at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha districts of Wolaita zone of SNNPR during main cropping season, 2023. The districts are among the major wheat-growing areas of the Wolaita zone and selected based on the production potential of wheat and a hot spot for the development of wheat rusts diseases epidemics. The three experimental sites are geographically located at 06° 85' 28" N and 037° 76' 10" E (at Kokate), 06° 88' 79" N and 037° 80' 18" E (at Dalibo Wogane) and 06° 52'55" N and 037° 49' 15" E (at Zala Shasha). The sites are found at an elevation of 2156 (at Kokate), 2200 (at Dalibo Wogane) and 2105.94 (at Zala shasha) meters above sea level. Bimodal rainfall pattern is the major characteristics of the study area, short rainy season (April and May), and the main rainy season (early June to mid-November). Thus, the areas receive average annual rainfall is 1200- 1300 mm and mean monthly temperatures varies from 11-26 °C. The soils are sandy-loam with a PH of 5.2.

Treatments, Design of Experiment and Management Procedures

The experiment was conducted during 2023 main cropping season and natural infestation was considered as the main source of inoculums. The total width and length of the layout were designed at 34 x 33 m with a unit plot size of 10 x 10 m, respectively. Plots were spaced by 1.5 m and blocks separated by a safeguard path of 2.0 m to prevent drifts or cross-contamination. The study was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Sowing was practiced on 11 July 2023 simultaneously in the three locations, at a 25 cm interval along the rows. Hidase variety, which is susceptible to yellow rust and stem rust, of wheat was used for the study. The recommended fertilizer rate of 100 kg ha⁻¹ of NPS was applied in rows during planting, while 200 kg ha⁻¹ of Urea was side dressed, of which 1/3rd of it during planting and 2/3rd of it 35 days after planting. A total of three treatments, including control, were comprised during the study. Wabe 300 EC at the rate of 0.5 L/ha in 200 liter of water (Candidate fungicide), Royal 750 WDG at the rate of 120g/ha in 160 liter water (Standard check), and unsprayed check were used. For the candidate fungicide, the use of the rate of fungicide per hectare and amount of water for dilution of fungicide was performed as suggested by the manufacturer. Spraying was performed using a manual knapsack sprayer. The fungicides application was started at 35, 40 and 42 days after planting when the first symptom of yellow rust was appeared in the plots at Kokate, Zala Shasha and Dalibo Wogane districts, respectively. The fungicides were applied for two times within the 15-day intervals on each plot. Unsprayed plots were left for each replication as controls to allow maximum disease development. Regular weeding and earthing up were practiced to all plots uniformly manually when necessary in all three locations.

Disease Assessment

Stem rust and yellow rust intensity were estimated by the respective proportion of the diseased leaf, for yellow rust and stem, for stem rust of a plant was used. The assessment was carried out at weekly intervals and ceased with the crop attaining physiological mature. Twenty randomly selected wheat plants from the middle rows of each plot were used for all disease severity assessments. A total of five assessments were made per location. Stem and yellow rust severity were scored visually on the selected plants for each disease using the modified Cobb's Scale described by (Peterson *et al.* 1948). The mean yellow and stem rust terminal severity were used for the analysis. The rust severity was 0% = no visible rust infection with immune plant response; 20% = rust infection up to 20% of severity with small uridia present; 40% = rust infection up to 40% of severity with variable sized uridia present, some with chlorosis, necrosis or both; 60% = rust infection up to 60% of severity and medium sized uridia are present and possible surrounded by chlorotic areas; and 100% = rust infection up to 100% of severity and large sized uridia are present, generally with

little or no chlorosis and no necrosis. The mean stem and yellow rust terminal severity of the twenty plants of each plot was used for the analysis. The integral model, i.e., area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) was assessed for each disease at different days after planting for each plot applying the following formula (Wilcoxson *et al.* 1975).

$$\text{AUDPC} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} 0.5 (X_i + X_{i+1}) (t_{i+1} - t_i) \quad (1)$$

Where, X_i = percentage of disease severity index (PSI) of disease at i^{th} assessment; t_i = time of the i^{th} assessment in days from the first assessment date; and n = total number of disease assessments. Besides, data on visual observation on wheat crop phytotoxicity was assessed.

Data Analysis

Data on terminal severity of stem rust and yellow rust at the final assessment date, and respective AUDPC values were subjected to analysis of variance to determine the treatment effects. The treatment means were separated using the Fishers protected least significance difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level (Gomez and Gomez, 1984). The data analyses were conducted using the general linear model procedure of SAS software version 9.2 (SAS, 2009).

Results and Discussion

Effect of Wabe 300 EC Fungicide on Stem Rust Development and Yield of Wheat

Stem rust terminal severity, AUDPC and grain yield of wheat were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by the applications of fungicides across locations (Table 1). At all locations, the highest mean terminal severity and AUDPC for stem rust and lower grain yield was noted from the unsprayed control plots. Conversely, the lowest stem rust mean terminal severity and AUDPC and the highest grain yield was noticed from Wabe 300 EC sprayed plots next to it Royal 750 WDG sprayed plots in three locations (Table 1). There are statistically significant differences among Wabe 300 EC ($P < 0.05$) and Royal 750 WDG sprayed plot. Wabe 300 EC sprayed plots reduced stem rust terminal severity, AUDPC and increased grain yield of wheat when compared with other treatments. At Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha sites highest grain yields, lowest stem rust terminal severity as well as AUDPC were recorded on plots sprayed with Wabe 300 EC with (2634kg/ha, 2702kg/ha, 2811kg/ha, 30.41, 32.3, 28.7, 415.3, 407, 398.5) while the lowest grain yields, and the highest stem rust terminal severity as well as AUDPC were recorded from unsprayed control plot (1195.3 kg/ha, 1232kg/ha, 1319 kg/ha, 92.07, 87.5, 89.7, 1306, 1426.3, 1319.5) respectively (Table1). Generally, the significant difference in AUDPC, terminal severity and grain yield values among the evaluated fungicide might be due to the characteristics nature of the product formulations.

Table 1. Effect of Wabe 300 EC Fungicide on Severity and Area under Disease Progress Curve of Stem Rust and Yield of Wheat at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha during 2023 Cropping Season

Treatments	Kokate			Dalibo Wogane			Zala Shasha		
	TS (%)	AUDPC (%)	GY	TS (%)	AUDPC (%)	GY	TS (%)	AUDPC (%)	GY
Wabe 300 EC	30.41c	415.3c	2634 a	32.3c	407c	2702a	28.7c	398.5c	2811a
Royal 750 WDG	43.72b	501.6b	2062.3b	48.2b	510.7b	2201b	40.3b	465.9b	2312b

Unsprayed check	92.07a	1306a	1195.3c	87.5a	1426.3a	1232c	89.7a	1319.5a	1319c
LSD (0.05%)	12.14	70.8	23.5	14.03	89.6	105.7	10.7	92.5	109.4
CV (%)	25.06	13.8	19.5	21	15.4	21.7	19.3	21	19.5

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. TS = Terminal Severity; AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve; GY = grain yield (kg/ha); CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level.

Effect of Wabe 300 EC Fungicide on Yellow Rust Development

The results of the effect of the two fungicides on yellow rust terminal severity and AUDPC in the three locations are shown in Table 2. Analysis of variance revealed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in yellow epidemic development was observed between the sprayed fungicides, Wabe 300 EC and Royal 750 WDG, across locations. In three experimental locations, Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha, analysis of variance, shows that minimum mean yellow rust terminal severity and AUDPC were noticed from plots sprayed by Wabe 300 EC, followed by Royal 750 WDG sprayed plots at the final date of assessment in all locations (Table 2). In other words, minimum mean yellow rust terminal severity and AUDPC were recorded from plots sprayed with Wabe 300 EC and Royal 750 WDG as compared to the unsprayed plots in the three locations (Table 1). The fungicide Wabe 300 EC effects on yellow rust showed consistent results across locations. Earlier researchers reported that wheat disease severity was reduced only by using a frequent application of systemic fungicide (Saari and Prescott, 1975; CIMMYT, 2005). Overall, the effectiveness of Wabe 300 EC could be an active ingredient in its formulation targeted at yellow rust. It is possible to deduce that two times foliar sprays at 15 day intervals effectively reduces the magnitude of yellow rust severity and increases grain yield of wheat.

Table 2. Effect of Wabe 300 EC Fungicide on Severity and Area under Disease Progress Curve of Yellow Rust at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha during the 2023 Cropping Season

Treatment	Kokate		Dalibo Wogaane		Zala Shasha	
	Terminal severity (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	Terminal severity (%)	AUDPC (%-day)	Terminal severity (%)	AUDPC (%-day)
Wabe 300 EC	31.5bc	510.8c	32.4c	483.5c	34.5c	512.3c
Royal 750 WDG	52.72b	618.2b	49.63b	593.8b	53.4b	583b
Unsprayed check	122.97a	1415a	125a	1243.2a	105.2a	1197.9a
LSD (0.05%)	18.3	102.9	15.6	87.9	17	65.9
CV (%)	28.03	29.6	25	31.5	19.75	14.75

Means in the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance. AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve in %-day; CV = Coefficients of variation (%); and LSD = Least significant difference at $p < 0.05$ probability level.

Conclusions and Recommendation

Wheat stem and yellow rust causes serious problems in the study areas during the production season. The grain yield was highly affected by stem and yellow rust diseases. The results revealed that the treatments with high stem and yellow rust severity and AUDPC, respectively had

minimum grain yield at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha; whereas the treatments with maximum protection (Wabe 300 EC) give higher grain yield at Kokate, Dalibo Wogane and Zala Shasha followed by Royal 750 WDG relative to the untreated control. During the growing periods, no foliar toxic effect was observed from the effect of any tested fungicides. Generally, results showed that Wabe 300 EC foliar application at the rate of 0.5 L/ha with 200 liter water per hectare was highly effective in controlling yellow and stem rust of wheat and increased grain yield of wheat. Hence, Wabe 300 EC was found highly effective for the control of stem and yellow rust and therefore it is recommended for registration for the management of stem and yellow rust in wheat production.

References

- Agrios, G. N. (2005). *Plant Pathology* (5th ed.). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Anteneh, A., & Asrat, D. (2020). Wheat production and marketing in Ethiopia: Review study. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 6(1), 1778893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2020.1778893>
- CIMMYT (International Center for Maize and Wheat Improvement). (2005). Sounding the alarm on global stem rust: An assessment of race Ug99 in Kenya and Ethiopia and the potential for impact in neighboring regions and beyond. Expert Panel Report. International Center for Maize and Wheat Improvement.
- CSA (Central Statistical Agency). (2021). Agricultural sample survey, 2020/2021: Report on area and production of crops (Private peasant holdings, main season) (Vol. 1, No. 590). Central Statistical Agency, Ethiopia.
- Eshetu, B., & Zerihun, K. (2003). Integrated management of Septoria blotches of wheat: Effect of sowing date, variety, and fungicide. *Journal of Pest Management*, 7(11-18).
- Eyal, Z. (1999). The Septoria tritici and Stagonospora nodorum blotch diseases of wheat. *European Journal of Plant Pathology*, 105(7), 629-641. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008727402683>
- FAOSTAT. (2021). Food and Agriculture Organization: Production of wheat: Top 10 wheat producers in 2019.
- Ghaffary, S. M., Faris, J. D., Friesen, T. L., Visser, R. G., van der Lee, T. A., & Robert, O. (2012). New broad-spectrum resistance to septoria tritici blotch derived from synthetic hexaploid wheat. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*, 124(1), 125-142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-011-1692-3>
- Gomez, K. A., & Gomez, A. A. (1984). *Statistical procedures for agricultural research* (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Green, M. B., Le Baron, H. M., & Moberg, W. K. (1990). *Managing resistance to agrochemicals: From fundamental research to practical strategies*. American Chemical Society. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bk-1990-0421>
- Hailu, E., & Woldeab, G. (2015). Survey of rust and Septoria leaf blotch diseases of wheat in central Ethiopia and virulence diversity of stem rust *Puccinia graminis f. sp. tritici*. *Advanced Crop Science Technology*, 3(2), 2-5.

- Hei, N., Tesfaye, T., Woldeab, G., Hailu, E., Hundie, B., Kassa, D., & Gebrekirstos, T. (2018). Distribution and frequency of wheat stem rust races (*Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*) in Ethiopia. *Journal of Agriculture and Crop Research*, 6(5), 88-96.
- Marja, J., Janne, K., Björn, A., Andrea, F., Lise, N. J., Antanas, R., Timo, K., Jens-Erik, Ø., & Annika, D. (2020). Yield increases due to fungicide control of leaf blotch diseases in wheat and barley as a basis for IPM decision-making in the Nordic-Baltic region. *European Journal of Plant Pathology*, 158, 315–333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-020-02057-0>
- Peterson, R. F., Campbell, A. B., & Hannah, A. E. (1948). A diagrammatic scale for estimating rust intensity on leaves and stems of cereals. *Canadian Journal of Research*, 26(4), 496-500. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cjr48c-033>
- Roelfs, A. P. (1985). *The cereal rusts: Diseases, distribution, epidemiology, and control* (Vol. II). Academic Press.
- Saari, E. E., & Prescott, J. M. (1975). A scale for appraising the foliar intensity of wheat diseases. *Plant Disease Reporter*, 59, 377-380.
- SAS Institute. (2009). *SAS/STAT user's guide* (Version 9.2). Cary, NC: SAS Institute Inc.
- USDA (United States Department of Agriculture). (2022). Foreign agricultural service: World agricultural production global analysis (Circular series WAP 2-22). USDA.
- Wilcoxson, R. D., Skovmand, B., & Atif, A. H. (1975). Evaluation of wheat cultivars for ability to retard development of stem rust. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 80, 275-2181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7348.1975.tb01620.x>
- Zegeye, T., Taye, G., Tanner, D., Verkuyl, H., Agidie, A., & Mwangi, W. (2001). Adoption of improved bread wheat varieties and inorganic fertilizer by small scale farmers in Yelmana Densa and Farta districts of Northern Ethiopia. *EARO and CIMMYT*, 3-5.

